

Business and Ethical Decision Making For Corporate Efficiency: A Case of Royal Bank of Scotland

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Abstract

This study assessed Business and Ethical Decision Making for Corporate Efficiency: A Case of Royal Bank of Scotland. An extensive review of related literature was carried out, as such, findings from preceding studies formed the pivot of this research piece. Business and Ethical Decision Making for Corporate Efficiency form professional views. The study of ethics is said to be focused on the choices facing an individual because, as a person brings in his or her personalities into the group; the standards of the group decision, would be forced to shape their values and behaviors. Therefore, to study ethics in management requires studying both the basis of an individual choices and how a group or organization ensures that the decision-making standards are followed. Other aspects include ethical leadership in organizations, decision-making process for business efficiency, business and ethical decision-making for business efficiency. While it was recommended that the entire business system needs an overhaul starting with, involving the employees as regards ethical behavior of organizations in the decision making process because they are assets of any organization, management should be morally ethical in their decisions to boost company's reputation and finally by improving on the internal structures though enabling the free flow of information to aid transparency in organization's business activities.

Keywords: *Business, Ethics, Business Ethics, Management, Business, Organization, Manager, Ethical, Decision-making, Ethical Leadership*

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Managing any organization either as a CEO, Board member or manager requires making decisions that are ethically inclined, some of which pose some complexities. Ethical standards serve as an extension of the legal requirements from not just doing things right but doing the right thing. The process of ethical consideration and legal obligation that the leadership of the organization possess is focused on governance, due diligence and responsibilities to stakeholders, particularly the end users (NCOSS, 2012). Moreover, even people in private organizations are charged with the duty of making sound ethical decisions as, management have a general responsibility to tackle difficult issues through an ethical dimension within their business. They are also called to demonstrate and practice the values, objectives and aims of the organization. Furthermore, managers and staff are also expected to exhibit their ethical intelligence by handling issues, from the very serious and challenging one's to the basic day-to-day problems (NCOSS, 2012).

Nevertheless, the term business ethics has been understood differently by various organizations due to the un-specific definition associated with ethical related issues. The phrase often overlaps words like; morals, principles, values and ethics. Consequently, to support an understanding of business ethics, these terminologies will be specifically described to include, morals which, refers to a personal or singular view about what is wrong or right as, a person may use moral or personal convictions in making an ethical decision (Ferrell, Fraedrich and Ferrell, 2013). Business Ethics refers to the moral or ethical dilemmas that may occur in a business setting. The objective is to show the difference between right and wrong as to equip people with the tools for dealing with moral complexities and, to identify and think through the moral implications of a strategic decision (Robert, 1992). Values are said to be the beliefs an individual holds true and factual. And, most of the values in the modern-day organizations include; teamwork, trusts, integrity and accountability - based on organizational best practices.

However, ethical decision-making deals with moral issues and, a moral issue is made evident where individual actions when freely performed, may cause potential harm or benefit to others. Thus, the decision or action must have consequences for other people. Therefore, ethical decision is defined as a decision that is both legal and morally acceptable to the larger society whereas, unethical decision may be registered as either illegal or morally unacceptable to the larger community (Jones, 1991). Nevertheless, the study of ethics is said to be focused on the choices facing an individual because, as a person brings in his or her personalities into the group; the standards of the group decision, would be forced to shape their values and behaviours. Therefore, to study ethics in management requires studying both the basis of an individual choices and how a group or organization ensures that the decision-making standards are followed (Naylor, 1999). Moreover, several and well documented scandals where, leaders' unethical behaviour depict severe consequences for organizations and their surroundings has uncovered a need for modern organizations to recognize and deal with complex business ethics (Gallespie, 2009). Most researchers have often confused the phrase, ethical business with corporate social responsibility. And, it is imperative to distinguish between ethical business practices and corporate social responsibility programs. For, it is a firm's duty to establish programs that are socially responsible and the place for employees to act in an ethically responsible manner. In any case, employees working in reputable organization can nevertheless take actions that are seen as unethical (Grewal and Levy, 2012).

Basically, most managers have been perceived to face ethical predicaments, and this arises as a result of the intentions of different parties involved or affected by conflicting decisions, as a party cannot achieve benefits, without disadvantaging the other. Also, in a bureaucratic organization, interest of equity in decision-making is made to apply, and to affect all members, clients and stakeholders (Henk, 1994). In this study, it is the researchers' intentions to draw knowledge from various theoretical frameworks in relation to the decisions taken on ethical dilemmas, explore ethical leadership in organizations and focus on the ethical decisions and the outcomes of Royal Bank of Scotland (RBS) and thus, conclusion and recommendations follow afterwards.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this includes the following:

1. To examine the significance of ethical leadership in organisations
2. To analyse the decision-making process for business efficiency with focus on Royal Bank of Scotland
3. To assess the impact of business and ethical decision-making for business efficiency

The other parts of these research paper is organized into other subdivisions. The evaluation of related and significant literature is enclosed in section two with other subhead extensively discussed, while discussion of findings conclusion and recommendations are stated in the last part of the section.

2. Literature Review

3. 2.1 Ethics and Theoretical Framework

There are many theories on the traditions and classification of ethical principles but, for this study, the researchers considered four dominant theories to include the Deontology, Utilitarianism, Virtue Ethics and Relativism. Naylor (1999) described three of the theories as follows:

Deontology, by origin is the science of duty. It refers to the process that involves directing our reasoning according to the basic deals that are 'almost' universal in nature. The caveat almost entails that rules might be set out on the right direction but along the way, exceptions to this rules may be discovered. For instance, the question of, is it right to offer a bribe and win a business agreement? As, the purpose of the bribe is to benefit from a preferential treatment as against putting other business negotiators at a disadvantage position, if such actions are predicted right for an individual then, the action is right for every other individual. Additionally, difficulties emerge when people discover exceptions or when there seem to be conflicting principles.

In contrast the Utilitarianism methodology, does not take into account consequences because, a moral course is believed and widely approved by administration and businesses, as a tool that provides the greatest good for the greatest number of people. This notion also, provides a platform for a capitalist market arrangement

and for, business and organization survival. However, there are some criticisms on the utilitarianism approach. First, there is the possibility of an unfair distribution of benefits of a particular achievement as, minor advantages for many could be overshadowed by major disadvantages for few. Secondly, the approach addresses itself as a distinct action and, does not provide general advice as to what is wrong or right. Thirdly, the system has some complexities as; it could put up a single principle and yet, suffers from difficulties with the greatest good. Finally, its democratic and practical principles breakdown when confronted by real circumstances.

Furthermore, the model of virtue ethics sees morality as a set of attitudes and behaviour established among groups and societies. It supports and justifies the idea of moral education, which is training and developing individuals to act according to the expectations of the society of what is right and wrong. For instance, in organizations, those who see management as a professional practice expects all managers to adhere to the common goals and standards of good behaviour. Basically, majority of the people behave virtuously for obvious reasons of seeking to be seen as fair, strict, friendly, reliable, honest and so on. Also, to be known as a virtuous person reduces transaction cost, accelerate deals, gain credit and have promises accepted without desiring for guarantees or carrying out an investigation. Additionally, a person is accepted into an association of like-minds that operate transparently and efficiently. However, one limitation of this model is the area of difficulty arising as a result of conflicting virtues. For example, an individual may come from a society that does not tolerate noise in the classroom and at the same time possess tolerance. Does the tolerance prevent a person's condemnation from minor noise disturbance by others? Such problems are most likely evident in businesses. These problems are associated with resolving empowerment and control, personal improvement and completing a task (Naylor, 1999). Nevertheless, ethical disagreements and skepticism about the rational resolution of moral disputes is one aspect of the problem gave rise to the theory of relativism. Cultural or descriptive relativism put forward that; disagreements on morality exist in different cultures and several times within a particular culture. Therefore, ethical or moral relativism normatively posits that, there is and cannot be only one correct rational morality or set of values for all the societies.

Relativism extensively holds that; morality is a social concept that enables any moral system to be possible in any society. It also, affirms that judgment of good and evil should not be done intrinsically or universally. Some critiques of moral system, perceive it as ideological in nature whose, fundamental role is to sustain the ruling class. Additionally, Epistemological relativism and postmodern skepticism gave birth to ethical relativism and claims that, in all human endeavors, there can be no objective or universal language. Furthermore, the extreme form of relativism conflicts a correspondence in moral virtues across all stable cultures as, virtues and values forms part of human nature, human needs and common problems which, are critical for the survival of the society. Ultimately, the difference that exist in moral norms are said to be minimal and, emerges only as a result of social and historical contexts, beliefs and ideologies that shape moral norms to an extent. However, these differences are less important when compared to the foundation of core values associated with the common problems that must be solved to ensure communities survival (Grcic, 2013)

Further to the theories above, the essence of ethics deals with the rules that channel behaviour towards a particular path basically, towards a good path. More so, all ethical decisions are guided by the underlying values of an individual or person as the value system of an individual directs a person towards assuming ethical or unethical decisions thus, ethics becomes a system of rule that governs the ordering of values.

It is therefore significant for organizations to consider the implication or consequences attached to their decisions also, reflecting on the greatest good for a greater number of people as proposed by the utilitarianism approach under the act-utilitarianism (Bateman & Zeithaml, 1993)

Decision-makers could select among conflicting values the alternative with the greatest positive impact on greater number of people. Additionally, an individual or group interest must not override stakeholders or overall corporate interest as proposed by Frederick Taylor 1914 in the universal principles of management. Nevertheless, since people have different value system consequent on their background, education, emotion, intelligence etc. it is paramount for businesses or corporations to explicitly identify, define and establish measures to control decisions.

2.1 Ethical Leadership in Organizations

The ethics of business practice and leadership in organizations has become prevalent in contemporary organizations, as ethical behaviour and effective leadership are linked and inseparable. Goffe and Jones (2000) highlights that effective leaders seldom show their weaknesses and make known their differences and, are intuitively endowed and engage employees by practicing tough empathy. However, experiential research also confirms that, leaders whose profession is ethically inclined will ultimately succeed and those who lacks ethical base will eventually fail (Butcher, 1997). Nevertheless, Katz and Khan (1978) emphasized that, leadership may be seen as a product of one's position, as a set of personality traits, as a set of observable behaviour, as dependent upon the situation in which it is exercised and as, dependent upon how a leader and the followers react and interact with each other.

Robbins et al. (2009) defined leadership as an influence directed towards others in a given situation in order to actualize specific goals. Further seen as, dynamic relationship between leaders and followers through goal settings and achievement that affects work groups activities.

Also, some business analyst argues that, ethics and other principled steps towards leadership are not sustainable as a result of competition and the aspiration for flexible leaders. Additionally, the socialist and moralist point of view about business ethics has always proven to be of great importance as, corporate sectors have identified a need to adopt this approach in view of actualizing their objectives. However, ethical leadership is said to begin with personal values, examination and, a reflection on one's core values because, self-mastery is a tool that creates a platform for ethical leadership. Moreover, what is paramount is, what top executives are seen to do aside their normal routines because, their actions can reinforce a corporate culture and in turn, determine the way low level employees act and respond when faced with ethical dilemmas. Nonetheless, Bethel (1999) posits that, a leader who con-currently practice high ethics and exercises genuine concern, competence and fairness towards others, is by so doing sending a clear message as well as establishing trust. On the contrary, when there is a mismatch in the professed standards, it sends a clear sound that, authenticity and integrity is lacking, as followers will be misled, and the lack of trust might ruin the ability to lead, inspire and to make a difference.

However, Kohlberg (1984) developed the best explanation for how people make ethical decisions. Furthering that, to aid an individual moral behaviour, they must decide what course of action is morally right and then select the morally right path over others. Also, suggesting that, maturity is obtained through times when a dilemma present itself in a way that it cannot be resolved, explained or go against current personal beliefs. Furthermore, French and Granose (1995) argued that, leaders at the upper echelon of management take more of ethical decisions because; they are overwhelmed with the normative ethical principles of justice and right. Primarily, there were initially six stages of cognitive moral development but, were further streamlined to three including; pre-conventional, conventional and post-conventional levels. Consequently, the pre-conventional level indicates that, the right kind of behaviour is highly decided by the rewards, punishments and favours linked with one's actions and level of involvement. Accordingly, Petrick and Quinn (1997) enunciates that, an autocratic or coercive, path goal and transactional leadership style is highly frequent in this level of development and, the outcomes for organizations would likely be, a strong focus on task accomplishment as, rules and regulations act as a means ensuring compliance.

At the conventional level of moral development, what is indicated as right is generally focused on the roles and expectations of others, abiding by rules and regulations and the fulfilment of duties and obligations. Although, this construct depicts trust and loyalty, as people are bound to respond to task and directions as a way of pleasing the leaders and authority. Hence, typical leadership is seen to revolve around, situational style of leadership and, the outcomes would be building cohesive groups and competitiveness, encouraging teamwork and assisting individuals to be part of the team, which will be emphasized in the culture. Moreover, emphasis at the later stage, will shift focus towards respecting; internal authority and authority figures, maintaining compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks and, aid leadership authority (French and Granose, 1995)

Finally, the post-conventional level at this stage explains that, people are more concerned with making decisions on a principled basis, are consistent with justice and rights and, have gone beyond the idea of self-interest or referent groups. Additionally, the concept of moral law is practiced towards contributing to societal wellbeing and exists beyond the written laws. The leadership styles evident in this case includes, participative and servant-follower and, at the later stage comes transformational and empowered team

leadership. As a result, the likely outcomes will be emphasized on a democratic decision-making with further emphasis on communication of information and ethical implications as such.

Ultimately, Turner et al., (2002) identified that, leaders operating at higher levels of moral development are more likely to take decisions based on principled approaches taking into account, the rights of others and applying justice and equality in decision making process.

2.3 Decision-making Process for Business Efficiency in Royal Bank of Scotland

The Royal Bank of Scotland Group Plc., also known as RBS group, is a British banking and insurance company offering a variety of services ranging from personal banking and business banking to private banking, insurance and corporate finance. The organization is also known as the second largest bank in Europe and have branches spread across European countries and, assets worth \$ 1120 billion. Consequently, the bank has demonstrated a rhetorical public image as a good neighbor yet, through arts and sports sponsorship, the environment and society has suffered severe environmental damage. Most of which includes, forcing open new carbon frontier, causing environmental degradation, disturb indigenous people and increase conflicting issues in majority of the countries particularly, West Africa and the Caribbean. The worst aspect of their lending is on the long-term and by standards; new rigs and pipelines only start pumping five years down the line and proceed till about 20 years. However, it is anticipated that the decision made on the maximization of short-term profits could still be causing climate harm beyond the year 2030 (Palluelo, 2007).

RBS, which was bailed by the tax payers in 2008 are now 84 percent owned by the government and have recently engaged in some financial deals with the Belarusian government of which the outcome was shameful as, it emerged at a time when the bank is under surveillance. Report also carried that, earlier this month, the Royal Bank of Scotland along with the British high street bank have been allegedly accused of investing a huge sum of money in companies that produce cluster bombs, irrespective of the ban in the manufacturing and trading of weapons (The Independent, 2014). Furthermore, there were some specific factors that led to the failure of RBS around 2007/2008 that is, during the financial crisis and, this was ascribed to some specific decisions that were made by the Board and senior management of Royal Bank of Scotland to include, keeping RBS lightly capitalized in order to maintain an efficient balance sheet and also, adopting a business standard that was highly dependent on wholesale funding. These approaches are termed as creative accounting which, refers to the transformation of the figures in financial accounting from the original state to what the management desires by capitalizing on loopholes in the accounting principles to create a desired image of the organization (Naser, 1993)

Additionally, as a result of the crisis in 2008, RBS called for a review of the board and chairman's committee, which was an appropriate step towards improving on those events. However, the review team laid hands on no evidence concerning the failing of governance but, the overall outcome reveals that, the RBS board and chairman's committee were instrumental to the failure of the bank due to the unethical decisions that took place as such, they were blamed and made to take responsibility for their actions. Moreover, the review team concluded that, even if the governing process lacks evidence, there were still some substantive failures as a result of the decisions made by the Board. The decisions made in RBS are discovered to be top-down and responsibilities are ascribed to the board and senior management afterwards. Further to the financial crisis in 2007/2008, the evidence available has made it difficult to reach a conclusion on, how RBS management, governance and culture affected the quality of their decisions but the review team analysis raised the following questions: whether RBS set bonuses for the CEO which made him focus more on increasing revenue, profit, assets and leverages rather than concentrating on capital liquidity and quality of assets. Whether the management style by the CEO was coercive and discouraged robust and effective challenge or questioning. Whether the mode of operation by the board including executive confrontations was in line with the formal process. Additionally, during that period, majority of the board members including the CEO were replaced and blamed for the Bank failures but, this decision had a repercussion as, most of the members replaced were familiarized with the system (Elpidorou, 2013). Aside the internal management in RBS, there were also some irregularities and multiple of flaws in the financial service authority as, concerning the acquisition of ABN AMRO which was one aspect that led to their failures, Mr. Sant who was then, head of the division of wholesale and institutional marketing division confirmed that, during that period, the then executives of RBS did not reveal any decision on the merits of the deal and there was no financial consideration of it in the executive committee or the Board and, this

reflected a severe weakness in the corporate governance of the Financial Service Authority (FSA) (The Telegraph, 2011)

Moreover, RBS then, had a large and fast expanding investment banking operation and was entirely controlled by the retail marketing division separate, from the wholesale and institutional marketing division that was known to have experience in banking operations. Mr Sant, who was the then head of department, claimed to have not been consulted and has made several attempt to oversee some aspects of the regulations in RBS but, all effort proved abortive. Although some members of the board claimed there was no written evidence to support Sant propositions. The FSA report stipulates that, assumptions towards an attempt to decrease risk in the financial sector are geared towards mitigating the regulatory and supervisory failures of the FSA as well as, market inadequacies in the regulation and supervision of capital, liquidity and asset quality, which posed a serious indictment on the chairman and executives in place at the time, including their predecessors irrespective of the dominant political gravities (HCTC, 2013)

Nevertheless, according to an interview with the current CEO of RBS, Ross McEwan, the steps taken to fix the past oversights includes, concentrating efforts now on the values and cultures embedded in the system to be more visible and ensuring to apply high standards to their decision-making process. Further stating that, RBS is currently involved in regulatory investigations accusing past manipulations of interbank rates of borrowing. Redressing highlighted concerns over lending and investment habits by ensuring that, two thirds of lending decisions are carried out locally by the area expert and, establish websites to avail the public of the information RBS uses to make a lending decision and finally, advance complex lending decisions. (RBS, 2013). Also, the CEO hopes to reduce investment risk towards issues that have the potentials to threaten the sustenance of the business as well as resolve its task affairs and lending practices especially in sectors like the oil industry, mining and forestry that have the tendencies to go wrong (Sharp, 2014)

2.4 Business and Ethical Decision-Making for Business Efficiency

It is interesting to know that a lot of people have spent their greater time to outline their personal ethics and how they intend to behave, the term business ethics in recent time started to come under extreme scrutiny. This is as a result of Enron who was at the center of serious indignity in connection with its 2001 irregular financial practices (Vitale and Cull 2018), it looks from then that high profile business decision-makers were in the media practically on daily basis as there were being rebuked for business deception, exploitation and greed. And in reaction to public scandal, it was however an essential decision by business community in general who started much concentration on boosting business ethical practices with a validated and practicable listing proper rules for ethical practice for workers for adherence. However, the study of business is occasionally mentioned as an applied ethics because it tries to interpret social contract theory, deontology, utilitarianism and other theoretical philosophies as extensively discussed above into suitable rules for conduct in various real world situations (Ferrell et al., 2019)

The idea of business ethics has come to mean numerous things to different people, in general, it is the knowledge and practice about business dealings that is moral or immoral within the workplace and doing what is appropriate (Payne et al., 2019). This is in regard to effects of products/services and in relationships with stakeholders. Omand and Phythian (2018) elucidate that devotion to business ethics is essential through times of needed transformation, times such as the one confronted by corporations presently, both nonprofit or for-profit organizations. Whereas, in times of vital adjustments, values that were earlier not seen as valuable are presently been examined. Beside, lots of these values are no longer followed. Business ethics is further seen as the behavior that an organization adheres to in its everyday practice across the globe (Singer, 2018). A certain organization ethics can be diverse because it may apply not only to how the business interacts with the world at large, but also to their daily practice and business operations with a single customer (Schwepker, 2018). Therefore, there is no clear moral compass to guide leaders through complicated problems as regard what is moral or immoral. The present business devotion to ethics in places of work is generally to sensitizes firms' workforces and managers on the best way to behave while doing business. Possibly and most essential, responsiveness to ethical behavior in workplaces assists in ensuring that when managers and leaders are trying in times of perplexity and crisis, they maintain a resilient ethical compass. In other words, this study further observes that attention given to business ethics in recent time is known to have provided several other benefits such as improvement in brand reputations to firms who behave ethically sound as well.

Snezhko and Coskun (2019) contend that a lot of businesses are having cruel image just by doing business. To a lot of people, the ultimate goal of businesses is of making money, and to them that is the bottom line and nothing more. This might be christened as capitalism in its realest form. Conversely, the practice with such firms with the goal of making money is not totally unreasonable. But the approach and techniques which most business organizations manage their firms that can raise the question for such an organization's ethical behaviour. It is significant for firms that suitable business ethics ought to be a measure for their daily business practice. Numerous international businesses, comprising of some foremost brands out there that the public make use of on daily basis, are understood not to be considering business ethics extremely of importance. Majority of these brands have been charged with millions of money in disobedience of ethical business laws. In all of this, money is the key determining element. In all, it may only be the sole option of the public to ensure that organizations follow appropriate business ethics (Trevino and Nelson, 2016). It is mostly known that when most corporations are making huge sums of money from their businesses, they tend not to give due and adequate attention to their business ethical behavior. There are countless businesses organizations that satisfy themselves with their correct business ethical behavior, but in this modern business rivalry domain across the globe, they are becoming extremely uncommon and far between.

As regards ethical decision making for business efficiency, Lynn (1994) explained that a lot of organizational managers believe that business ethics is an issue of individual moralities, a personal matter between individuals involved and their principles. These managers are fast to portray any misconduct in the organization as an isolated occurrence, and as the activity of a rascal worker. A general consideration that an organization might take or bear the liability for an individual's wrongdoings cannot be part of their thoughts. With such in mind, they believe that business ethics, generally does not have anything to do with organizations' management. Patterson and Rowley (2019) countered this thought that in fact, business ethics has a lot to do with management of organizations which are seen as the key players and policy makers. Hardly do the charisma weaknesses of a sole player completely describe business misbehavior. More typically, an organization immoral business activities comprises of obscure if not explicit, collaboration of others and reveals the morals, language, behavioral patterns, beliefs and mindsets that describe an establishment's working philosophy. It is significant to note that ethics can be seen as personal issue as much an organizational issue too. Leaders of organizations who ignore offering appropriate management and to introduce structures that enable upright business conduct, integrity strategy and share obligation with those who envisage, implement, and consciously benefit from business transgressions (Lynn, 1994).

In terms of an integrity strategy, (Lynn (1994) further posits that it is wider, deeper and more challenging than a legitimate obedience initiative. Wider in sense that it strives to facilitate trustworthy business behavior. Deeper in this regard that it cuts to the character and working structures of organization members and her corporation, their regulatory ethics and kind of their actions and thought. And more challenging because it entails an operational energy to explain the objectives and duties that establish an establishment's ethical compass. Melkevik (2018) further observe that ultimately, corporation's ethics is perceived as the sole job meant for management of organizations. Corporate advice could play part in the planning and execution of integrity strategies, nevertheless managers or leaders of organizations across the various levels and at all roles are integrated in the procedure as shown the diagram below for strategies for ethics management adapted from (Lynn (1994).

Strategies for Ethics Management	
<p>Characteristics of Compliance Strategy</p> <p>Ethos conformity with externally imposed standards</p> <p>Objective prevent criminal misconduct</p> <p>Leadership lawyer driven</p> <p>Methods education, reduced discretion, auditing and controls, penalties</p> <p>Behavioral Assumptions autonomous beings guided by material self-interest</p>	<p>Characteristics of Integrity Strategy</p> <p>Ethos self-governance according to chosen standards</p> <p>Objective enable responsible conduct</p> <p>Leadership management driven with aid of lawyers, HR, others</p> <p>Methods education, leadership, accountability, organizational systems and decision processes, auditing and controls, penalties</p> <p>Behavioral Assumptions social beings guided by material self-interest, values, ideals, peers</p>
<p>Implementation of Compliance Strategy</p> <p>Standards criminal and regulatory law</p> <p>Staffing lawyers</p> <p>Activities develop compliance standards train and communicate handle reports of misconduct conduct investigations oversee compliance audits enforce standards</p> <p>Education compliance standards and system</p>	<p>Implementation of Integrity Strategy</p> <p>Standards company values and aspirations social obligations, including law</p> <p>Staffing executives and managers with lawyers, others</p> <p>Activities lead development of company values and standards train and communicate integrate into company systems provide guidance and consultation assess values performance identify and resolve problems oversee compliance activities</p> <p>Education decision making and values compliance standards and system</p>

Figure 1: Strategies for Ethics Management, Adapted from: (Lynn, 1994)

In nutshell, in order to make efficient business ethical decisions for success, business managers and organizational leaders as a matter of necessity recognize and embrace their responsibility in influencing firms' business ethics and take this chance to design an atmosphere which is capable of improving the connections and image on which their corporations' achievement and efficiency depends on. Managers who are found disregarding morals are running the danger of falling into both corporate and individual burden of our present-day increasing and aggressive legal business environment. Furthermore, these dispossess establishments of advantages that may be accessible under new federal rules for punishing institutions condemned of business misconduct. These kind of punishing rules identify for the first time the executive and organizational origins of illegal behavior and base fines relatively in consideration of the degree of steps taken by corporations to avoid the wrongdoing.

3 Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, it is seen that in every structural organization including RBS, decision-making processes usually come from the upper echelon of the organization including, executives and non-executive directors, CEO's and managers. However, the outcomes of decisions are also seen to affect all members of an organization. In the case of RBS, the decision on investing in the oil industry that disturbs the neighborhood with oil spillages and causing environmental degradation as well as investment in bomb manufacturing industry, was taken by the board members and the CEO but, the outcome of the decisions affected the company's reputation and in-turn affected members working under the organization. At this stage the democratic decision-making process was not considered and the subordinates conformed to the decisions, which was more or less a coercive, Paternalistic or servant-follower style of leadership. The style of leadership in every organization has a significant role in the performance of the organization as, different situations warrant a separate kind of leadership. Nevertheless, situations must have led RBS executives to

carry out certain decisions that were critical to the establishment. Moreover, they were seen to have a weak internal control system, which was ascribed to the leaders of the organization for their lack of concentration on the core business activities. Basically, the entire system needs an overhaul starting with, involving the employees in the decision making process because they are the assets of any organization, be morally ethical in their decisions to boost company's reputation and by improving on the internal structures through enabling the free flow of information to aid transparency in business activities.

However, a disreputable company image can inhibit the effort of any organization. Therefore, the overhaul should be focused more on trying to restore the company image through corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities to the affected community which can help to boost the company image before attempting to fix other areas internally. The option of social responsibility is to appeal to the community or stakeholders for the detriment caused by the lopsided decision of the management of RBS.

Nevertheless, involving the subordinates of RBS in the decision-making could have helped in a wide range of viewpoints or opinions that would have averted the negative impact caused by the centralized decision-making adopted by the organization.

Also, sharing decisions with the employees leads to greater acceptance of outcome thereby lifting the burden off the shoulders of those in the hem of affairs. It is therefore, unethical to centralize decisions that is consequential to the entire organization or stakeholders. Moreover, stakeholders should not suffer the outcome of decisions that was made by a relatively few people hence, there should be a review on the policies and ethical consequences of a centralized decision.

Finally, RBS should integrate the code of ethics in their corporate philosophy as individuals have different personal ethical standards. The code of ethics is one of the most visible signs of corporate commitment to ethical behaviour. They should clearly define, write and tailor their code of ethics to the philosophy of the organization and, to enable the functionality of the code of ethics, special mechanisms for raising ethical concerns and questions should be considered. This may be actionable through creating anonymous suggestion boxes and an open door policy for the stakeholders. RBS can go further to appoint an ethical ombudsman to act as an ethical component of major corporate decisions and a sounding board for raising ethical concerns or decisions. These guidelines can influence critical decisions and would help decision-makers to avoid inadvertent breaches of ethics.

References

- i. Butcher, W.C (1997) *ethical leadership, executive excellence province* (14) 5-6
- ii. Bethel, S.M (1999) *a leader has high ethics, food management* (34) 36
- iii. Clegg, S., Komberger., M and Pitsis., T (2008) *managing and organisation: An introduction to theory and practice, 2nd edn, sage publication limited, London.*
- iv. Elpidorou, P. (2013) *the financial crisis and its impacts: a pre and post crisis financial assessment on RBS*
- v. http://www.academia.edu/3531673/The_financial_crisis_and_its_impact._A_pre_and_post_crisis_financial_assessment_on_RBS {ACCESSED: 2nd December 2018}
- vi. Ferrell, O.C., Fraedrich, J and Ferrell, L (2013) *Business ethics, ethical decision-making and cases, 10th edn, Cengage learning, U.S.A*
- vii. Ferrell, O.C., Harrison, D.E., Ferrell, L. and Hair, J.F., 2019. *Business ethics, corporate social responsibility, and brand attitudes: An exploratory study. Journal of Business Research, 95, pp.491-501.*
- viii. French, W and Granose, J (1995) *practical business ethics, Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, N.J.*
- ix. Gallespie, N and Dietz, G (2009) *trust repair after an organisation-level failure, Academy of Management Review, 34 (1) 127-145*
- x. Grcic, J (2013) *virtue theory, relativism and survival, international journal of social science and humanity, 3 (4) 416* <http://www.ijssh.org/papers/273-C10018.pdf> {ACCESSED: 4th December, 2018}
- xi. Grewal, D and Levy, M (2012) *Marketing, 4th edn, McGraw-Hill, New York*
- xii. Henk, V.L (1994) *Business ethics: the field and its importance, in Harvey, 12-13*
- xiii. Goffe, R and Jones, G (2002) *why should you lead anyone? Harvard Business Review, 62-70*
- xiv. Patterson, L. and Rowley, C., 2019. *Ethical management and leadership: a conceptual paper and Korean example. Asian Journal of Business Ethics, pp.1-24.*
- xv. Petrick, J and Quinn, J (1997) *management ethics: integrity at work, sage, and thousand oaks.*

- xvi. Robert, C.S (1992) *ethics and excellence: Oxford University Press, New York*
- xvii. Robbins, S.P, Millet, B and Waters-Mash, T (2004) *organisational behaviour, prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs*
- xviii. Jones, T.M (1991) *ethical decision making by individual in organisation: An issue contingent model, Academy Management Review, 16 (2), 366-395*
- xix. Kohlberg, L (1984) *the psychology of moral development: moral stages and the life cycle, Harper and Row, San Francisco.*
- xx. Lynn, S. P. 1994. *Managing for Organizational Integrity. Harvard Business Review. (Assessed Online), Available on: <https://hbr.org/1994/03/managing-for-organizational-integrity> (Accessed 20th January, 2019)*
- xxi. Mahonypartners (2012) *the failure of the Royal Bank of Scotland available on: <http://mahonypartners.files.wordpress.com/2012/01/rbs-part2management.pdf> Accessed: 6th September 2018}*
- xxii. Melkevik, Å., (2018). *A Theory of Business Economics: The Means–Ends Relation in Business Ethics. Journal of Business Ethics, pp.1-13.*
- xxiii. Naylor, J. (1999) *Management, Financial Times Prentice Hall, United Kingdom*
- xxiv. NCOSS, (2012) *Ethical decision making, management of information unit, information sheet 13.*
- xxv. <http://ncoss.org.au/projects/msu/downloads/resources/information%20sheets/13-ethical-decision-making-2012.pdf>{ACCESSED: 6th September 2018}
- xxvi. Naser, K. (1993) *creative financial accounting, its nature and use: Prentice Hall, Hemel Hempstead.*
- xxvii. Omand, D. and Phythian, M., 2018. *Principled Spying: The Ethics of Secret Intelligence. Oxford University Press.*
- xxviii. Paluello, M.M (2007) *according to friends of the earth Scotland, the Royal Bank of Scotland is rapidly accelerating our planet towards its climatic tipping point by financing fossil fuel extraction.*
- xxix. <http://www.ethicalconsumer.org/commentanalysis/corporatewatch/royalbankofscotland.aspx>{ACCESSED: 5th September 2018}
- xxx. Payne, D.M., Corey, C., Raiborn, C. and Zingoni, M., 2019. *An applied code of ethics model for decision-making in the accounting profession. Management Research Review.*
- xxxi. Schwepker, C.H., 2018. *Strengthening Customer Value Development and Ethical Intent in the Salesforce: The Influence of Ethical Values Person–Organization Fit and Trust in Manager. Journal of Business Ethics, pp.1-13.*
- xxxii. Sharp, T (2014) *RBS aims to lead from front on ethical banking*
- xxxiii. <http://www.heraldsotland.com/business/company-news/rbs-aims-to-lead-from-front-on-ethical-banking.23968738>{ACCESSED: 6th September 2018}
- xxxiv. Singer, A., 2018. *Justice failure: Efficiency and equality in business ethics. Journal of Business Ethics, 149(1), pp.97-115.*
- xxxv. Snezhko, S. and Coskun, A., 2019. *Liability or Ethics? The Real Value of Compliance. In The Circular Economy and Its Implications on Sustainability and the Green Supply Chain (pp. 198-212). IGI Global.*
- xxxvi. *The Independent (2014) RBS helped Bankroll Europe's last dictator.*
- xxxvii. <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/business/news/rbs-helped-bankroll-europes-last-dictator-2345509.html> {ACCESSED: 5th September 2018}
- xxxviii. *The House of Commons (2013) the FSA report into the failure of RBS*
- xxxix. <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201213/cmselect/cmtreasy/640/640.pdf> {ACCESSED: 5th September 2018}
- xl. Thomas S. Bateman and Carl P. Zeithaml (1993) *Management Function and Strategy, 2nd Edition, Irwin Sydney, Australia*
- xli. Turner, N. Barling, J. Epitropaki, O. Butcher, V and Miner, C (2002) *transformational leadership and moral reasoning, (87) 304-311*
- xlii. *The Telegraph (2011) RBS crisis, FSA wasn't worried as the storm approached*
- xliii. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/newsbysector/banksandfinance/8364907/RBS-crisis-FSA-wasnt-worried-as-the-storm-approached.html>
- xliv. {ACCESSED: 2nd September 2018}
- xlvi. Trevino, L.K. and Nelson, K.A., 2016. *Managing business ethics: Straight talk about how to do it right. John Wiley & Sons.*

- xlvi. Vitale, C. and Cull, M., 2018. *Modelling the influence of CEO values and leadership styles on financial decision making. The Journal of New Business Ideas & Trends*, 16(1), pp.16-30.
- xlvii. RBS, (2013) *RBS sustainability review 2013*.
- xlviii. http://www.google.com.ng/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=sf5&source=web&cd=54&ved=0CC0QFjADODI&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.banktrack.org%2Fmanage%2Fems_files%2Fdownload%2Frbs_sustainability_review_2013&ei=DtsOVPD_Mc7H7AbRsYDgAw&usg=AFQjCNGQS98krJbVp_qyZimgBFeUhbCnKw&bvm=bv.74649129,d.ZGU {ACCESSED: 5TH November 2018}

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